

The stability and breakdown of passive oxide films on metallic anodes[†]

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The passive oxide film on metals in aqueous solutions is stable (corrosion-resistant) to the extent that the Fermi level at the film/solution interface remains within the electronic energy band gap of the film (in the state of electronic band edge level pinning). Transpassivation that leads to a potential-dependent dissolution of the passive film occurs in the range of electrode potential in which the Fermi level is pinned in the electronic valence band level at the film/aqueous solution interface. Chloride adsorption introduces the surface state of electronic acceptor levels on the passive oxide film. When the Fermi level of passive metal anodes is pinned at the chloride-induced surface state, the localized transpassive dissolution of the passive film proceeds at the chloride adsorption sites to cause a local film breakdown. The critical potential for the local film breakdown appears less anodic (more negative) than the general transpassivation potential.

The passive film on metal anodes in aqueous solutions is stable in a limited range of electrode potential between the passivation potential and the transpassivation potential. The range of potential for the passive state of metal anodes depends on the nature of the metal; it is wider for iron than for nickel in acidic solutions^{1,2}.

In the presence of chloride ions the local breakdown of passive films occurs in the range of potential of the otherwise stable passivity. Fig. 1 schematically shows a typical polarization (potential versus current) curve of anodic dissolution of pure metals in acidic solutions. In general, the

Fig. 1. Schematic polarization curve of anodic dissolution of metals in acidic solutions containing passivity-destroying chloride ions. E_p = the passivation-depassivation potential, E_b = the film-breakdown potential, E_{pit} = the pit initiation potential, E_{TP} = the transpassivation potential

chloride-breakdown of passive films occurs at potentials more anodic (more positive) than a critical potential, called the film-breakdown potential, E_b . The breakdown of passive films is followed by the pitting mode of localized dissolution of passive metals, provided that the electrode potential is more anodic than the potential of pit-initiation, E_{pit} , frequently called the pitting potential. The pit initiation potential, E_{pit} , does not necessarily coincide with E_b . If E_{pit} is more anodic than E_b , the breakdown site on the passive film is repassivated at potentials less anodic than E_{pit} as has been observed with chloride-pitting of stainless steels in acidic solutions³. If E_{pit} is less anodic (more negative) than E_b , the breakdown site of the passive film inevitably grows into a stable pit; this may be the case of iron electrodes in acidic solutions⁴.

The local breakdown of passive films is a process associated with the film itself; this process is different from the process of pitting dissolution of passive metals^{1,2}. The film breakdown depends on the stability of the passive film against chloride ions, whereas the pitting dissolution is controlled by the stability criterion of localized dissolution of substrate metals¹⁰. The mechanism of breakdown of the passive film has been one of the most important subjects of corrosion science⁵⁻⁷. The pitting dissolution is also important in practice and its stability criterion has been a subject of intense study⁵⁻¹⁰.

The present paper discusses the anodic stability of metallic passivity from the standpoint of the electronic energy levels of passive oxide films and proposes a mechanism of

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anodic film breakdown in which the adsorption of chloride ions leads to a mode of localized transpassive dissolution of the passive film.

Distribution of electrostatic potential across passive oxide films :

The electrostatic potential at a metal anode covered with a passive oxide film is distributed across the metal/film interface, $\Delta\phi_{M/F}$, in the film, $\Delta\phi_F$, and across the film/aqueous solution interface, $\Delta\phi_{H1}$ ($=\Delta\phi_{F/S}$)¹¹, as shown in Fig. 2. In the electronic equilibrium between the metal and the oxide

Fig. 2. Profiles of the electrostatic potential and electronic energy level across a passive oxide film on a metal anode under the conditions of (a) flat band and (b) anodic polarization; ϕ = the inner potential, ϵ = electron energy, ϵ_F = Fermi level, ϵ_C = the conduction band edge level, ϵ_V = the valence band edge level, CB = conduction band; VB = valence band, Sol = aqueous solution, OHP = the outer Helmholtz plane.

film, a difference in the electrostatic inner potential, $\Delta\phi_{M/F}$, arises across the metal/film interface, the magnitude of which is represented by the difference in the chemical potential of electrons, μ_e , between the metal and the film as defined by eq.(1),

$$\Delta\phi_{M/F} = \frac{\mu_{e(M)} - \mu_{e(F)}}{e} \quad (1)$$

which forms an electric double layer at the metal/film interface consisting of excess or deficient electrons on the metal side and charged excess ions or ion vacancies on the film side. There also arises a difference in the electrostatic outer potential, $\Delta\psi_{M/F}$, between the metal and the film; this difference in the outer potential corresponds to the difference in the real potential of electrons, α_e , and hence in the nega-

tive work function, $-\Phi$, of the two phases as defined by $\Delta\psi_{M/F} = (\alpha_{e(M)} - \alpha_{e(F)}) / e = -(\Phi_M - \Phi_F) / e$. The interfacial potential difference forms a space charge layer (so called the Schottky barrier) on the film side at the metal/film interface. This space charge layer is considered to be very thin, probably one or two atomic layers, because of a high concentration of interfacial ionic point defects, electronic interface states and dipoles at the metal/film interface.

In the steady state of the passive oxide film, the transfer of metal ions takes place across the metal/film interface either by a process to annihilate metal ion vacancies (eq. 2a) or by a process to produce oxide ion vacancies (eq. 2b) in the film,

where M_M^{2+} is the metal ion in the metallic bonding, $O \cdot V_{M(MO)}^{2-}$ is the metal ion vacancy combined with oxide ions in the film, $M \cdot V_{O(MO)}^{2-}$ is the oxide ion vacancy combined with metal ions in the film, and MO is the oxide.

If the transfer of metal ions is at quasi-equilibrium (with a small rate of metal ion transfer) in the steady state, the activity, a , of interfacial vacancies is given by eq. (3a) for metal ion vacancies and by eq. (3b) for oxide ion vacancies at the metal/film interface,

$$a_{V_{M(MO)}^{2-}(M/F)} \approx a_{V_M^{2-}}^0 \exp\left(\frac{-2e\Delta\phi_{M/F}}{kT}\right) \quad (3a)$$

$$a_{V_{O(MO)}^{2-}(M/F)} \approx a_{V_O^{2+}}^0 \exp\left(\frac{2e\Delta\phi_{M/F}}{kT}\right) \quad (3b)$$

where a^0 is the activity of interfacial vacancies at $\Delta\phi_{M/F} = 0$, and k the Boltzmann constant.

The transfer of metal ions also occurs across the film/aqueous solution interface either by a process to produce metal ion vacancies (eq. 4a) or by a process to annihilate oxide ion vacancies (eq. 4b) in the film,

where M_{aq}^{2+} is the hydrated metal ion in the solution, $M^{2+} \cdot O_{MO}^{2-}$ is the metal ion combined with oxide ions in the film, and $M \cdot V_{O(MO)}^{2+}$ the metal ion combined with an oxide ion vacancy.

The transfer rate of metal ions across the film/aqueous solution interface depends on the potential drop at the interface, $\Delta\phi_H$ (across the Helmholtz layer)¹¹, and the dissolu-

tion current of the film, i_M , is given either by eq. (5a) for the process associated with metal ion vacancies or by eq. (5b) for the process associated with oxide ion vacancies,

$$i_{M(V_M)} = i_{M(V_M)}^0 \left(1 - \theta_{V_{M(MO)(F/S)}^{2-}} \right) \exp \left(\frac{\alpha e \Delta \phi_H}{kT} \right) \quad (5a)$$

$$i_{M(V_O)} = i_{M(V_O)}^0 \theta_{V_{O(MO)(F/S)}^{2-}} \exp \left(\frac{\alpha e \Delta \phi_H}{kT} \right) \quad (5b)$$

where $\theta_{V_{M(MO)(F/S)}^{2-}}$ is the ratio of the interfacial metal ion vacancies, $V_{M(MO)(F/S)}^{2-}$ the total sites of interfacial metal ions, $\theta_{V_{O(MO)(F/S)}^{2-}}$ the ratio of the interfacial oxide ion vacancies, $V_{O(MO)(F/S)}^{2-}$ the total sites of interfacial oxide ions on the film, and α the Tafel constant for the ion transfer. Eqs. (5a) and (5b) show that the transfer current of metal ions (dissolution current of the film) is an exponential function of $\Delta \phi_H$.

There is also the transfer of oxide ions across the film/aqueous solution interface as expressed by eqs. (6a) and (6b),

where H_{aq}^+ is the hydrated proton in the solution. In the steady state of passive oxide films in which the film thickness remains constant, the transfer of oxide ions is in the state of equilibrium so that the activities of metal ion vacancies, $\alpha_{V_{M(MO)(F/S)}^{2-}}$, and oxide ion vacancies, $\alpha_{V_{O(MO)(F/S)}^{2-}}$, at the film/aqueous solution interface are given by eqs. (7a) and (7b), respectively,

$$\alpha_{V_{M(MO)(F/S)}^{2-}} = K a_{H_{aq}^+}^{-2} \exp \left(\frac{2e \Delta \phi_H}{kT} \right) \quad (7a)$$

$$\alpha_{V_{O(MO)(F/S)}^{2-}} = K' a_{H_{aq}^+}^{-2} \exp \left(\frac{-2e \Delta \phi_H}{kT} \right) \quad (7b)$$

indicating that with increasing $\Delta \phi_H$ the activity of the interfacial metal ion vacancy increases and the activity of the interfacial oxide ion vacancy decreases.

In general, it has been established that the potential drop, $\Delta \phi_H$ (the difference in potential across the Helmholtz layer) at the oxide/aqueous solution interface is determined by the acid-base hydroxylation of the interface^{12,13}, giving rise to a pH-dependent potential drop at the oxide/aqueous solution interface as expressed by $\Delta \phi_H = \text{const} - 2.3026 k T \text{pH}$. Therefore, in a solution of constant pH, the interfacial potential drop $\Delta \phi_H$ between the passive oxide film and the aqueous solution remains constant, provided that the inter-

face is in the state in which *the electronic band edge level is pinned* as described shortly.

Under the anodic polarization, an electrostatic potential drop arises in the passive film as shown in Fig. 2. In the steady state of the passive film on pure metals, the anodic dissolution current of the passive film is constant and independent of the electrode potential, but the thickness of the passive film increases linearly with the anodic potential. Further, the interfacial potential drops, $\Delta \phi_{M/F}$ and $\Delta \phi_H$, both at the metal/film and at the film/aqueous solution interfaces remain unchanged at constant current of the film dissolution in the potential range of passivity.

Anodic stability of passive oxide films on metals :

In the steady state of a passive film, the rate of formation of the film (anodic transfer of metal ions across the metal/film interface combined with anodic transfer of oxide ions across the film/aqueous solution interface) equals the rate of dissolution of the passive film (anodic transfer of metal ions coupled with the cathodic transfer of oxide ions across the film/aqueous solution interface). Consequently, the transfer of oxide ions across the film/aqueous solution interface is at equilibrium giving rise to a constant film thickness at constant electrode potential. Whence, the dissolution current of passive metals is represented by the rate of anodic transfer of metal ions across the film/aqueous solution interface (the rate of dissolution of the passive film); this dissolution rate is determined by the potential drop $\Delta \phi_H$ at the film/aqueous solution interface^{1,11} as shown in eqs. (5a) and (5b).

In the range of potential of the passive state, the anodic dissolution current (passivity-maintaining current) of pure metals is independent of the electrode potential as illustrated by the anodic passivity of iron electrodes in acidic solutions; this potential-independent dissolution current means that the potential drop $\Delta \phi_H$ across the film/aqueous solution interface remains constant independently of the electrode potential.

In the range of potential of the transpassive state, the anodic dissolution current of metals increases with increasing anodic potential even in the presence of an interfacial oxide film (the transpassive film) on the metal surface. Similarly to the passive film, the thickness of the transpassive oxide film in the steady state remains constant at constant electrode potential and the potential-dependent dissolution current represents the transfer rate of metal ions across the film/aqueous solution interface (the rate of dissolution of the transpassive oxide film). The transpassive dissolution is caused by the quasi-metallization of the surface of the passive semiconductor oxide film due to the surface degen-

eracy of electronic energy eigenstates^{1,8,9}; with the degenerated surface of the passive film the potential drop $\Delta\phi_H$ across the film/aqueous solution interface increases linearly with increasing anodic potential in the potential range of transpassivity.

The passive oxide film is usually a semiconductor in which the electronic energy level is characterized by the conduction and the valence bands. In the range of potential of the passive state, the passive oxide film is *in the state of band level pinning* at the film/aqueous solution interface so that the interfacial potential drop, $\Delta\phi_H$, remains constant independently of the electrode potential of the passive metal; hence, the potential drop $\Delta\phi_F$ in the passive film increases with increasing anodic polarization. Therefore, in the range of electrode potential of the passive state, the anodic dissolution current of the passive film is potential-independent and the thickness of the passive film increases linearly with increasing anodic potential. Fig. 3 shows that the band level pinning is maintained to the extent that *the Fermi level of the passive film remains within the energy gap* between the conduction band and the valence band at the film/aqueous solution interface.

As the anodic polarization increases, the Fermi level, ϵ_F , at the film/aqueous solution interface is lowered until it reaches the valence band edge, ϵ_V , at which *the Fermi level, ϵ_F , is pinned*. In this state of Fermi level pinning at the valence band, a further increase of the anodic polarization

Fig. 3. Potential drops $\Delta\phi_H$ at the film/aqueous solution interface and $\Delta\phi_F$ in the passive film as a function of anodic potential E of a passive metal anode without any electronic surface states on the film; the film/aqueous solution interface is in the state of band edge level pinning to the extent that the Fermi level ϵ_F remains within the band gap, and it is in the state of Fermi level pinning when ϵ_F overlaps the valence band edge ϵ_V .

causes an increase of the potential drop not in the passive film but across the film/aqueous solution interface as shown in Fig. 3. Then, the interfacial potential drop, $\Delta\phi_H$, increases linearly with increasing anodic polarization and the transpassive mode of potential-dependent metal dissolution results.

Fig. 4 shows the anodic polarization curve in the steady state of an iron electrode in a sulfuric acid solution¹. The passive oxide film on iron electrodes is an *n*-type semiconductor (a ferric oxide, $\gamma\text{-Fe}_2\text{O}_3$) with the band gap of about 1.6 eV^{14,15}, and there is a relatively wide energy gap (≈ 1.3 eV) between the valence band edge, ϵ_V , and the Fermi level, ϵ_F , at the flat band potential (≈ 0.43 V)¹⁶; thus, the transpassivation potential, E_{TP} , is 1.3 V more anodic (more positive) than the flat band potential, E_{fb} , as shown in Fig. 4.

Fig. 4. Anodic polarization curve of an iron electrode in a sulfuric acid solution, showing that the transpassivation occurs beyond a certain potential (E_{TP}) where the Fermi level ϵ_F is pinned at the valence band edge ϵ_V ; E_{TP} = transpassivation potential, E_{fb} = flat band potential, E_p = passivation-depassivation potential, i_{Fe} = anodic iron dissolution current, i_{O_2} = anodic oxygen current.

With nickel electrodes on which the passive film is a *p*-type oxide (a nickel oxide, NiO), the energy gap between the valence band edge and the flat band Fermi level, ϵ_F , is small (≈ 0.2 eV) so that the transpassivation potential E_{TP} is relatively close to the flat band potential as shown in Fig. 5^{1,17}. The transpassive dissolution current of nickel anodes in acidic solutions has been found to increase as an exponential function¹⁷ in agreement with eq. (6) theoretically derived on the assumption that the passive film is in the state of Fermi level pinning.

It is evident from Figs. 4 and 5 that the passive film of n -type oxide is more stable than the passive film of p -type oxide against the anodic dissolution of passive metals.

In the case of iron and nickel electrodes described in the foregoing, the dissolution of the passive and transpassive oxide films proceeds in the mode of non-oxidative dissolution in which the anodic transfer of metal ions across the film/aqueous solution occurs without any increase or decrease in the ionic valence of metal ions (Fe^{3+} ion and Ni^{2+} ion). There are other modes of potential-dependent dissolution of the passive oxide film, such as oxidative dissolution illustrated by the anodic transpassive dissolution of chromium electrodes ($\text{Cr}_2\text{O}_3 + 4 \text{H}_2\text{O}_{\text{aq}} \rightarrow \text{Cr}_2\text{O}_7^{2-} + 8 \text{H}^+_{\text{aq}} + 6 e$) and the reductive dissolution illustrated by the cathodic dissolution of the passive oxide film on iron electrodes ($\text{Fe}_2\text{O}_3 + 6 \text{H}^+_{\text{aq}} + 2 e \rightarrow 2 \text{Fe}^{2+}_{\text{aq}} + 3 \text{H}_2\text{O}_{\text{aq}}$)¹⁸. Furthermore, the anodic dissolution of passive oxide films in which oxide ions are oxidized ($2 \text{MO} \rightarrow \text{O}_2 + \text{M}^{2+}_{\text{aq}}$) may take place¹⁹. These oxidative and reductive modes of dissolution of the passive film are not discussed in the present article.

Chloride-induced electronic surface states and anodic film breakdown :

Adsorption of a chloride ion on the passive oxide film occurs forming an adsorbed chloride complex ion and a metal ion vacancy as shown in eq. (8),

Fig. 5. Anodic polarization curve of a nickel electrode in a sulfuric acid solution, showing that the transpassivation starts to occur at a potential (E_{TP}) relatively close to the flat band potential E_{TB} because of the p -type nature of the passive oxide film on nickel^{1,17}.

where Cl^-_{aq} is the hydrated chloride ion, $\text{MCl}^+_{\text{ad}, \text{MO}}$ is the adsorbed chloride complex ion, and $\text{O} \cdot \text{V}^{2-}_{\text{M}(\text{MO})}$ is the metal ion vacancy combined with oxide ions in the film.

According to the chemistry of metal oxides²⁰, impurity anions with the negative ionic valence smaller than the oxide ion valence ($z = -2$) such as chloride ions ($z = -1$) generate localized electron acceptor levels in metal oxides. In the same principle, the adsorbed chloride ion, $\text{MCl}^+_{\text{ad}, \text{MO}}$ on the passive oxide film introduces a localized electron acceptor level on the surface of the film. It is also known that metal ion vacancies are the acceptor defects donating holes into the valence band²⁰. Therefore, the interfacial metal ion vacancy, $\text{O} \cdot \text{V}^{2-}_{\text{M}(\text{MO})}$, injected by the adsorbed chloride ions (eq. 8) also provides a localized electron acceptor level on the passive oxide film. These interfacial electron acceptors donate holes to the valence band of the film as represented by eqs. (9a) and (9b),

where h is the hole in the valence band, $\text{MCl}_{\text{ad}, \text{MO}}$ is the adsorbed chloride in the oxidized state of the electron acceptor of adsorbed chloride ion complexes, and $\text{O} \cdot \text{V}^{2-}_{\text{M}(\text{MO})}$ is the reduced state of the electron acceptor of interfacial metal ion vacancies. These surface states that form in the band gap between the conduction and the valence bands of the passive oxide film are schematically shown in Fig. 6 and expressed in eqs. (9a) and (9b).

Fig. 6. Surface states introduced by the adsorption of chloride ions at the oxide film/aqueous solution interface; ϵ_{SS} = the electronic surface state, Cl^-_{aq} = adsorbed chloride ion, V_M = metal ion vacancy introduced by the adsorption of chloride ions.

As the anodic polarization of a passivated metal electrode increases in the presence of a significant concentration of the surface states introduced by adsorbed chloride ions, the Fermi level, ϵ_F , of the passive film is pinned at the localized electronic level, ϵ_{SS} , of the chloride-induced surface state on the film/aqueous solution interface before it reaches the valence band level, ϵ_V , as shown in Fig. 7. As a

Fig. 7. Potential drops $\Delta\phi_H$ across the film/aqueous solution interface and $\Delta\phi_F$ in the passive film as a function of anodic potential E of a passive metal anode with and without the electronic surface states introduced at the film/aqueous solution interface by the adsorption of chloride ions; the interface is in the state of local Fermi level pinning at the adsorption sites of chloride ions when the Fermi level ϵ_F overlaps the surface state level ϵ_{SS} .

result of local Fermi level pinning at the surface state, the interfacial potential drop, $\Delta\phi_H$, across the film/aqueous solution interface increases locally at the sites of adsorbed chloride ions with increasing anodic polarization; hence, the localized potential-dependent dissolution of the passive film occurs at the chloride adsorption sites, while the remaining part of the film surface without chloride adsorption sustains the potential-independent dissolution in the passive state.

Such a localized potential-dependent dissolution of the passive film can be regarded as a *localized transpassive dissolution* of the film at the sites of adsorbed chloride ions. In the anodic potential scan of a passivated metal electrode, the localized transpassive dissolution begins to occur at a critical potential, E_b , which is less anodic (more negative) than the transpassivation potential, E_{TP} , at which the general transpassive dissolution begins to occur in the absence of chloride adsorption as shown in Fig. 8. The difference between E_{TP} and E_b corresponds to the difference between the valence band level, ϵ_V , and the localized level of the surface state, ϵ_{SS} ($= \epsilon_{a-}$), introduced by adsorbed chloride ions.

Fig. 9 shows the potential profile across the passive oxide film with and without chloride-induced surface states. In the absence of adsorbed chloride ions, the potential-independent dissolution of the passive film proceeds through a

Fig. 8. General transpassive dissolution that occurs at potentials more anodic than the transpassivation potential E_{TP} at which the Fermi level ϵ_F is pinned at the valence band edge ϵ_V and localized transpassive dissolution at the adsorption sites of chloride ions that starts to occur at the film-breakdown potential E_b at which the Fermi level ϵ_F is pinned at the surface state level ϵ_{SS} introduced by the adsorption of chloride ions.

Fig. 9. Local potential drop $\Delta\phi_H$ across the film/aqueous solution interface which locally increases at the adsorption sites of chloride ions with increasing anodic potential leading to a localized transpassive dissolution, to a local film thinning, and eventually to a local film breakdown.

constant interfacial potential drop $\Delta\phi_H$. In the presence of adsorbed chloride ions, the localized potential-dependent transpassive dissolution of the passive film occurs at the adsorption sites of chloride ions where the potential drop

across the film/aqueous solution interface locally increases with increasing anodic polarization. The locally increased transfer current of metal ions from the passive film into the aqueous solution results in a local thinning of the passive oxide film producing an increased metal ion transport in the film. Such a locally increased dissolution rate of the passive film in the transpassive mode can be regarded as a *local breakdown* of the passive film at the adsorption sites of chloride ions.

The critical potential at which the localized chloride-breakdown of the passive film starts to occur is called the breakdown potential of the passive film. As described in this section, the breakdown potential, E_b , of the passive film corresponds to the potential at which the Fermi level, ε_F , of the passive metal electrode reaches the chloride-induced surface state level, ε_{ss} ($= \varepsilon_{a-}$) and, hence, at which the localized transpassive dissolution starts to occur at the adsorption sites of chloride ions as shown in Fig. 9. Since the electronic level of the surface state, ε_{ss} ($= \varepsilon_{a-}$), is less anodic (higher in electronic energy) than the valence band level, ε_V , the breakdown potential, E_b , is less anodic than the general transpassivation potential, E_{TP} .

From the foregoing it follows that the critical potential, E_b for the chloride-breakdown of the passive film is characteristic of individual passive metals. It is also followed that the concentration of hydrated chloride ions appears to have no influence on the breakdown potential; however, as is described shortly, the probability of chloride-breakdown of the passive film increases with increasing concentration of chloride ions.

Probability of film breakdown :

In the steady state of a passivated metal electrode, the adsorption of chloride ions on the passive film (anodic transfer of chloride ions across the electric double layer on the film/aqueous solution interface) represented by eq. (8) is in the state of equilibrium. The Langmuir adsorption isotherm, which holds at small adsorption coverages, yields the coverage of adsorbed chloride ion complexes, $\theta_{MCl_{ad}^-}$, and the coverage of interfacial metal ion vacancies, $\theta_{V_{M(MO)(F/S)}}$, on the passive oxide film as a function of the interfacial potential drop, $\Delta\phi_H$, as expressed in eq. (10),

$$\theta_{MCl_{ad}^-} \theta_{V_{M(MO)(F/S)}} = K_{ad} a_{Cl_{aq}^-} \exp\left(\frac{e\Delta\phi_H}{kT}\right) \quad (10)$$

where K_{ad} is an adsorption constant, $a_{Cl_{aq}^-}$ is the activity of hydrated chloride ions in the solution. Since $\Delta\phi_H$ is constant in the potential range of the passive state, the coverage of adsorbed chloride ions is independent of the electrode potential.

Introducing eq. (7a) into eq. (10) yields eq. (11) for the coverages of adsorbed chloride ion complexes and interfacial metal ion vacancies,

$$\theta_{MCl_{ad}^-} (\theta_{V_{M(MO)(F/S)}})^{1/2} = K^* a_{Cl_{aq}^-} a_{H_{aq}^+} \quad (11)$$

where K^* is a constant. Eq.(11) shows that the coverages of the interfacial electron acceptors, $\theta_{MCl_{ad}^-}$ and $\theta_{V_{M(MO)(F/S)}}$, depend on the concentrations of hydrated chloride ions and hydrated protons and does not depend on the electrode potential in so far as the metal electrode is in the potential range of passivity.

It is assumed that the coagulation of some number of adsorbed chloride ions is probably required for the localized transpassive dissolution to occur at chloride adsorption sites. The probability of the breakdown of the passive film will increase as the concentrations of hydrated chloride ions and hydrogen ions increase in the solution. There arises a minimum concentration of hydrated chloride ions below which the chloride-breakdown of the passive film does not occur in the time span of interest as often observed in experiments.

Once the localized transpassive dissolution breaks out at an chloride adsorption site, the interfacial potential drop $\Delta\phi_H$ increases, thereby, giving rise to an increase of the equilibrium concentration of adsorbed chloride ion at the adsorption site as suggested from eq. (10). Consequently, the spot of localized transpassive dissolution will be enlarged autocatalytically by an increased localized film dissolution; hence, producing a film breakdown site of the order of micrometers large enough for pit-embryos.

As described in the foregoing section, the chloride-breakdown of the passive film is initiated with the localized transpassive dissolution of the film at the adsorption sites of chloride ions. In the case of iron anodes in aqueous solution, the chloride-breakdown of the passive film is followed by the pitting that is the localized metal dissolution at the film breakdown site. The transition from the film breakdown (localized film dissolution) to the pitting (localized metal dissolution) has been clearly recognized with an iron electrode in borate solutions⁴, in which an injection of chloride ions causes first to increase the localized dissolution of the passive film in the form of ferric ion Fe^{3+} followed by a sudden increase of pitting dissolution of the substrate metal in the form of ferrous ion Fe^{2+} . Further, the rate of localized dissolution of the passive film was observed to increase with increasing concentration of hydrated chloride ions in the solution⁴.

In the case of stainless steels in acidic solutions the local film breakdown does not necessarily produce the

stable pitting, unless a certain condition required for the stable growth of pitting is fulfilled as described in the literature¹⁰.

Conclusions :

(i) The passive oxide film on metal anodes is stable in aqueous solutions to the extent that the Fermi level of the film remains in the electronic energy gap between the conduction band and the valence band of the film; i.e. to the extent that the passive oxide film is in the state of *band level pinning*. In this state of band level pinning, the dissolution current of the passive film remains constant independently of the electrode potential of passive metal anodes.

(ii) The transpassivation of passive metal anodes occurs at potentials where the Fermi level of the passive film is pinned at the valence band of the film; i.e. the passive oxide film is in the state of *Fermi level pinning*. In this state of Fermi level pinning, the potential drop across the film/aqueous solution interface increases linearly with the electrode potential of passive metal anodes and the potential-dependent transpassive dissolution of the passive oxide film proceeds.

(iii) The adsorption of chloride ions on the passive oxide film introduces a localized electron acceptor level (a surface state) at the film/aqueous solution interface. When the Fermi level of passive metal anodes is locally pinned at the chloride-induced surface state, the *localized transpassive dissolution* of the passive oxide film proceeds leading to a local breakdown of the passive oxide film at the sites of adsorbed chloride ions. The critical potential (film-breakdown potential) for this mode of local breakdown of the passive film, at which the Fermi level is pinned at the chloride-induced surface state, is less anodic (more negative) than the general transpassivation potential.

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